

A Study to Assess the Myths Regarding Contraceptive Methods Among Women Residing in Selected Rural Area of Betul District to Develop Planned Teaching Programme

Dr. Sunita Choubey

Head of Department, obstetrics and gynecology Nursing in People's College of Nursing & Research Centre Bhopal.

Rupa Magarde

M.Sc. Nursing in obstetrics and gynecology Nursing.

Abstract:- A study to assess the myths regarding contraceptive methods among women residing in selected rural area of Betul district to develop planned teaching programme” The research design used in this study is descriptive survey design. Quantitative Non Experimental Research Approach was used in this study. The sample consisted 100 married women residing in selected rural area of Betul district M.P. Non probability convenient sampling technique was used for the selection of the subjects. The instrument used for the study was a self structured questionnaire. The assessment of overall myths regarding contraceptive method majority of the married women 75% had above myths, 13% of women had average myths and 12% of women had to below myths.

Keywords:- Myths, Contraceptive, Preventive, Pregnancy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Contraception (birth control) prevents pregnancy by interfering with the normal process of ovulation, fertilization and implantation.¹

Reproductive health is associated with many complex problems. There are complex issues such as health problem of women and children, sexually transmitted diseases, poverty, education, gender equality and human rights.

Women's percentage which is using any contraceptive method and prevalence rate of modern contraceptive rate is some but limited to women using modern contraceptive methods which include sterilization, condoms, oral hormonal pills, intra uterine devices etc. the unmet requirement for family planning is defined as the percentage of women who do not want any children or women want to delay the birth of new child for at least 2 years.²

II. NEED OF THE STUDY

Population growth is adversely affecting our national economy. There is no improvement in different areas due to the increasing population but the proper benefits of ongoing schemes run by the government have not even reached the people increasing family and increasing number of birth have

adversely affected the health of both mother and child, due to which the family society and country are getting hampered in becoming financially strong. Increasing birth and infant mortality and other obstetric complications, increasing gynecological complication and nutritional problem are occurring. This is the reason not only India, people all over the world are worried about the increasing population and the government is conducting awareness campaigns on this problem, but no conclusion is reached the goal. This direct effect of population growth is on studying the delicate balance of quality of life and nature. So that exploitation of the environment can be prevented and maternal infant mortality can be reduced so that people can get good life good education and better health.

Even after putting many efforts by the government no conclusion is being achieved. Because so many schemes are not being properly used by target groups. Still women are having so many misconception regarding use of various type of contraceptives. A health care team member its our prime responsibility to find out the misconception or myths regarding contraceptive methods and provide right information to the reproductive age women. So they can use various type of contraceptive methods and prevent unwanted pregnancies, limit their families and also contributing in decreasing maternal mortality death due to the frequent deliveries.

➤ Objectives

- To assess the socio demographic variables.
- To assess the myths regarding contraceptive methods among women.
- To develop planned teaching programme on myths regarding contraceptive method among women.
- To determine the association between myths regarding contraceptive methods and their selected socio demographic variables.

➤ Hypothesis

- **H0-**There is no significant relationship between myths regarding contraceptive methods and selected socio demographic variables among women.
- **H1-** There is significant relationship between myths regarding contraception method and selected socio demographic variables among women.

➤ *Assumptions*

- The rural women have some myths regarding contraceptive methods.

➤ *Delimitations*

- The study was be limited to only rural Women.
- The study was limited on 100 women’s.

III. METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH APPROACH:- , Quantitative research approach was used.

RESEARCH DESIGN:- non experimental descriptive survey design was used.

RESEARCH SETTING :- Pohar (rural area) of Betul district M.P.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:- Non probability convenient sampling technique was used.

SAMPLE SIZE:- 100

DEVELOPMENTAL TOOL

Part I : part first consist of total 15 item related to socio-demographical characteristics of women.

Part II : part second consist of total 24 item related to myths regarding contraceptive.

IV. MAJOR FINDING OF THE STUDY

➤ *Findings Related to Demographic Variable of Women*

Majority 42% of women were in the age group of 18-29 years. Majority 56% of husbands were in the age group of 41-50 years. Most of the women 28% were graduate group. Most of the women 22% were graduate group. Majority 26% women were in clerical/shop/farm group. The majority 59% husband were in clerical/shop/farm group.

SECTION – A

FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF MARRIED WOMEN ACCORDING TO SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

Demographic variables	Category	Students	
		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age	18 - 30 years	42	42.0
	31-40 years	40	40.0
	41-50 years	18	18.0
Husbands age	18-30 years	15	15
	31-40 years	29	29
	41-50 years	56	56
your qualification	Professional degree	0	0
	Graduate	28	28.0
	Intermediate/ diploma	4	4.0
	High school	22	22.0
	Middle school	19	19.0
	Primary school	27	27.0
	Illiterate	0	0
Husbands qualification	Professional degree	4	4.0
	Graduate	22	22.0
	Intermediate/ diploma	10	10.0

The highest proportion of the women 41% had a monthly family income of Rs. 1000-1999 per month. Majority 58% of women belonged to 15-20 years of age group at the time of marriage. Majority 42% of husband belonged to 23-28 year of age group at the time of marriage. Majority 37% of women living 2-4 number of the person in the house. Most of the women 51% were from joint family group. 100% of women the were Hindus. 66% of women receive information regarding contraceptive through TV. And Majority 100% of women know about contraception method. Majority 69% of women used any type of contraception.

➤ *Findings Overall Myths of Women Regarding Contraceptive*

The overall myths of the married women regarding contraceptive found to be high myths. In the study 75% of women had above myths, 13% of women had average myths and 12% of women had to below myths regarding contraceptive.

➤ *Finding Related to Association Between Knowledge Score and Selected Demographic Variable*

There was significant association between myths with selected demographic variables like religion and women know about contraceptive method.

There was no significant association between myths score with selected demographic variables like age, husbands age, qualification of women, husbands qualification, occupation of women, husbands occupation, family income, women age at the time of marriage, husbands age at the time of marriage, number of the persons living in the house, type of the family, source of information, used any type of contraceptive method.

	High school	14	14.0
	Middle school	19	19.0
	Primary school	18	18.0
	Illiterate	13	13.0
Your occupation	Professional	0	0
	Semi- professional	0	0
	Clerical/shop/farm	26	26.0
	Skilled worker	0	0
	Semiskilled worker	0	0
	Unskilled worker	0	0
	Unemployed	74	74.0
Husband's occupation	Professional	0	0
	Semi- professional	0	0
	Clerical/shop/farm	59	59.0
	Skilled worker	26	26.0
	Semiskilled worker	15	15.0
	Unskilled worker	0	0
	Unemployed	0	0
Family Income	Rs. 2000 and above	25	25.0
	Rs. 1000-1999	41	41.0
	Rs. 750-999	31	31.0
	Rs. 500- 749	3	3.0
	Rs. 300-499	0	0
	Rs. 101-299	0	0
	Less than Rs. 100	0	0
Your age at the time of marriage	15-20 year	58	58.0
	21-25 year	42	42.0
	26-30 year	0	0
Husbands age at the time of marriage	18-22 year	25	25.0
	23-28 year	43	43.0
	29-33 year	32	32.0
Number of the persons living in the house	2-4 members	37	37.0
	4-6 members	31	31.0
	6-8 members	20	20.0
	8-10 members	12	12.0
Type of the family	Nuclear family	42	42.0
	Joint family	51	51.0
	Extended family	7	7.0
What is your Religion	Hindu	100	100.0
	Muslim	0	0
	Sikh	0	0
	Other (please specify)	0	0
Source of information	T.V.	66	66.0
	Multi-media	11	11.0
	Friends	21	21.0
	Health care work	2	2.0
	Yes	100	100.0
	No	0	0
Do you have used any type of contraceptive method?	Yes	69	69.0
	No	31	31.0

Table 1

Fig 1:- Distribution of Married women by age in years.

Fig 2:- Distribution of Married women by husbands age in years.

Fig 3:- Distribution of Married women by their education.

Fig 4:- Distribution of Married women by their husbands education.

Fig 5:- Distribution of Married women by their occupation.

Fig 6:- Distribution of Married women by their husbands occupation.

Fig 7:- Distribution of Married women by their family income.

Fig.8:- Distribution of Married women by their age at the time of marriage.

Fig 9:- Distribution of Married women by their husbands marriage age.

Fig.10:- Distribution of Married women by their family members.

Fig 11:- Distribution of Married women by their family type.

Fig 12:- Distribution of Married women by their religion.

Fig 13:- Distribution of Married women by their source of information.

Fig 14:- Distribution of Married women by husbands occupation age in years.

Fig 15:- Distribution of Married women by their using any type of contraceptive method.

SECTION-B

Myths test knowledge score among married women regarding contraceptive.

Myths level	Category	Classification	
		Frequency	Percentage
Above myth	< 50%	75	75.0
Average myth	< 30%	13	13.0
Below myth	15%	12	12.0

Table 2

Fig 16:- Classification of married women myths score regarding contraceptive.

V. CONCLUSION

The study revealed that the overall myths of married women regarding contraceptive was high myths.

The study revealed that here was significant association between myths with selected demographic variables like religion and women know about contraceptive method.

The study revealed that there was no significant association between myths score with selected demographic variables like age, husbands age, qualification of women, husbands qualification, occupation of women, husbands occupation, family income, women age at the time of marriage, husbands age at the time of marriage, number of the persons living in the house, type of the family, source of information, used any type of contraceptive method.

REFERENCES

[1]. Dutta D.C. A textbook; Obstetrics including Perinatology and Contraception. Sixth Edition 2004. Publication; New central book agency (P) LTD, 8/1 Chintamoni Das Lane, Calcutta 700 009 (India).531.

[2]. New JR, Cahill N, Stover J, Gupta YP, Alkema L. levels and Trends In Contraceptive Prevalence, unmet need, and demand for family planning for 29 states and union territories in India: a modeling study using the Family Planning Estimation tool. Lancet Glob Health. 2017 Family Planning 2020 India Commitment Maker Since 2012
<http://www.familyplanning2020.org/india>

[3]. 2019 Family Planning Data Sheet Highlights Family Planning Method Use Around the World
<https://www.prb.org/2019-family-planning-data-sheet-highlights-family>

[4]. Family planning in India is based on efforts largely sponsored by the Indian government.
https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Family_planning_in_India

[5]. Fact sheet, Madhya Pradesh national family health survey
https://s.docworkspace.com/d/ALcStaq98_pT6fCMpeGdFA

[6]. Family Planning
https://s.docworkspace.com/d/AFebHTa98_pT0dk8peGdFA

[7]. Detailed Guidelines & Monitoring Modalities for the scheme of “Home Delivery Of Contraceptives By ASHAs”
<https://www.google.com/search?q=scheme+for+home+delivery+of+contraceptive+by+ashas&oq=sche&aqs=chrom>

[8]. Park K. A textbook; Preventive and social medicine. 19th edition. Bhanot: Publishers; 1167 premnagar, Jabalpur, 482,001(India)

[9]. Andrew M. Kaunitz,MD, importance of family planning and comparison of contraceptive efficacy,cost,and benefits
https://www.glowm.com/section_view/heading/the%20importance%20of%20Contraception/item/373#ref